

Characterizing the Carnot cycle at absolute zero: a reply to “Comment on ‘Proof of the Nernst theorem’ ”

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This reply addresses a recent comment concerning the proof of the Nernst theorem. I clarify how a Carnot engine can consistently operate at $T = 0$ through a continuous deformation of a cycle operating at $T > 0$. By examining the limit where heat exchange with the cold reservoir vanishes, I show that the Nernst theorem ensures that the concept of temperature remains physically consistent at the absolute zero limit.

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I appreciate the recent comment by Chen *et al.* [1] regarding my study on the proof of the Nernst theorem [2]. I concur with the Authors’ assertion that it is of the utmost importance to clarify the relationship “between the Carnot cycle and the fundamental laws of thermodynamics.” I offer this reply to clarify why the Nernst theorem [3]:

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow 0} (S(T, x_2) - S(T, x_1)) = 0, \quad \forall x_2, x_1 \in \mathcal{D}, \quad (1)$$

where x is a mechanical variable with domain $\mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{R}^+$, is directly derived from the statement of the Second Law. To put it simply: if the temperature T in Equation (1) is the Carnot temperature, and the entropy S is the Clausius entropy, then the theorem is a formal consequence of the Second Law [2].

Chen *et al.* [1] claim that the Carnot theorem “is only suitable for the temperature region of $T > 0$.” This aligns with Einstein [4]’s perspective at the Second Solvay Congress: by denying that a Carnot engine can operate “in practice” at $T = 0$, the Carnot theorem is deemed inapplicable at this limit, consequently restricting the temperature domain to $T > 0$.

In my view, this restriction is inconsistent with the framework of the Second Law, which establishes temperature as a primary consequence and provides its metric via the Carnot theorem. We do not restrict the domain of length to $L > 0$ by excluding $L = 0$; we do not restrict mass to $m > 0$; nor do we restrict the magnitude of heat exchanges to $Q > 0$. Consequently, we should not restrict the domain of temperature to $T > 0$. Instead, we should derive the implications of a null reversible heat exchange with the cold reservoir—the only consistent way to achieve $T = 0$ within the Second Law. That consequence is precisely the Nernst theorem.

This approach requires a conceptual characterization of a null measurement of T using a Carnot engine. In the

Discussion of the original study, I sketched such a procedure but certainly lacked sufficient clarity. I now offer a more detailed description based on a previous study [5].

The Carnot engine is a fundamental model because it is the simplest engine compliant with Planck’s statement of the Second Law: an engine with only two net heat exchanges—hence a binary engine. While this is typically achieved via two reversible isotherms and two reversible adiabats, it can also be realized through a cycle composed of two reversible isotherms exchanging entropy ΔS with high and low reservoirs, connected by two arbitrary paths that differ by a constant entropy shift equal to ΔS (see Figure 1). In this generalized construction, the heat and entropy exchanges along these paths cancel out, ensuring that the energy and entropy balances are governed by the same equations of a standard Carnot cycle.

At the high isotherm, ΔS is extracted by reversibly changing the mechanical parameter from x_1 to x_2 . For the low isotherm, the Nernst theorem implies the existence of a T^* such that $\Delta S^*(T^*, \mathcal{D}) = \Delta S$, where $\Delta S^*(T, \mathcal{D})$ is the change in entropy when the mechanical variable is extended across its entire domain \mathcal{D} (e.g., from zero to infinite magnetic field for a paramagnetic substance). With ΔS given, the working substance cannot perform this cycle at any temperature below T^* .

To decrease T^* , an experimentalist needs only reduce the change in x at the unit (high) isotherm so that ΔS decreases. However, at the low isotherm, the change in x continues to span the domain \mathcal{D} . As ΔS shrinks toward zero, x_2 continuously approaches x_1 at the high isotherm. At the low isotherm, the entropy exchange also shrinks to zero, yet the change in the mechanical variable continues to span the domain \mathcal{D} . In the limit $T = 0$, the four-stroke cycle degenerates into a reversible two-stroke path. Notably, at $T = 0$, no reversible isothermal change of x is required; the “cycle” simply contacts the isotherms at a single value of x . This degeneracy does not invalidate the construction; rather, it is expected for a null measurement—much like how the jaws of a caliper meet when measuring zero length. Einstein [4]’s remark no longer

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Figure 1. A Carnot cycle (black solid lines with arrows) where two isotherms are connected by two arbitrary paths with a constant entropy shift ΔS , maintaining the net balances of a standard Carnot cycle. The white area represents pairs of (S, T) accessible within the domain of x . The gray areas display non-accessible pairs of (S, T) within the domain of x . The temperature of the low isotherm T^* is determined by equaling the full range of entropy within the domain of x to the entropy ΔS exchanged at the high isotherm. By shrinking ΔS at the high isotherm, T^* continuously decreases, exemplified by the cycle in dashed stroke. The gray dotted line shows iso- x lines, with positive slope as required by stability. An animation of this plot is available as supplementary information doi:10.5281/zenodo.19127423.

applies because, in the limit, no change is attained at absolute zero. Importantly, the cycle operating at $T = 0$ is not a “reversible adiabatic cycle” as Chen *et al.* [1] suggest, but a reversible diathermal path spanning a finite range of temperature, but whose net heat and entropy balances are zero.

I must note that this construction is not possible with the standard Carnot engines (two isotherms and two adiabats) described by Chen *et al.* [1] and neither is possible when the Nernst theorem is negated and Einstein [4]’s remark accepted. For the standard engines, the limiting temperature is determined by the intersection of the reversible adiabatic path (a horizontal iso- S line) and the boundary of accessible states. In that framework, the experimentalist can never exhaust the domain of x at the low isotherm. Furthermore, as $T \rightarrow 0$, the temperature of the high isotherm cannot remain fixed, the extent of the reversible adiabatic path also shrinks, and the cycle eventually coalesces into a single point, instead of a finite, reversible, two-stroke, path. This explains why, after assuming the Nernst theorem, Liboff [6] concluded that at $T = 0$ “a Carnot engine does not exist and the Kelvin temperature scale is not defined,” a conclusion

clearly inconsistent with the fact that temperature is a fundamental physical observable.

Finally, if the Nernst theorem is negated while Planck’s statement is upheld, a similar construction fails. While one can move the low isotherm of a Carnot engine toward zero so that the heat exchange shrinks, if the entropy exchanged remains non-zero, then at $T = 0$ the engine ceases to exist “in practice,” as per Einstein [4] argument. No null measurement is achieved; it is simply excluded—this would be akin to a caliper disappearing the moment its jaws touch. It is this abrupt exclusion that is formally inconsistent with continuity and brings a series havocs [7]. In the published study and in this reply I only highlighted that $T = 0$ remains formally uncharacterized if the Nernst theorem is negated and Einstein [4]’s argument accepted. This is paradoxical for a physical observable deduced from a law of nature and is inconsistent the moment $T \rightarrow 0^+$ is present in the statement of the theorem. If the T in the theorem is Carnot’s temperature—the only temperature deduced from Planck’s statement—then the theorem is proven.

For completeness, I should add that the condition of stability ensures entropy remains finite at $T = 0$ [8, 9]. The fact that $S(U, x)$ is concave and its slope is infinite at $T = 0$ does not imply that entropy is unbounded. For instance, $S = \sqrt{U}$ is concave and finite as $\partial S/\partial U \rightarrow \infty$. The relationship between stability and thermodynamic properties at $T \rightarrow 0^+$ is best understood by analyzing $U(S, x)$, which is always convex, and is flat at $T = 0$. Given $U_{ss} = (\partial^2 U/\partial S^2)_x = T/C_x$, stability $U_{ss} > 0$ at $T = 0$ mandates that C_x vanishes at least as fast as T . This implies $U(S, x)$ is parabolic or subparabolic, ensuring the horizontal tangent at $T = 0$ is attained at a finite value of S .

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TIMELINE

The author received an email from the Editorial Office on March 3rd, 2026 informing him that the Comment by Chen *et al.* [1] had been accepted and inviting the Author to reply. The invitation was accepted after a reading of the Comment, and the reply was drafted and submitted on March 4th, 2026.

These events were coincidental with the drafting of the talk scheduled for March 6th 2026 at Conef VII.

The writing of the manuscript required 9 different `emacs` sessions from 2026-03-03 19:57 to 2026-03-20 08:22 .